

The values of \bar{n} obtained are of the order of 1 indicating the formation of 1 : 1 complexes of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) below the pH at which precipitation occurred. The values of \bar{n} were plotted against the corresponding values of pA and the value of pA at $\bar{n}=0.5$ corresponds to apparent stability constants $\log k_1$. Bjerrum⁶ introduced the spreading factor (x) for the determination of the corrected values of \bar{n} . The refined values of \bar{n} were then plotted against pA . The final value of $\log k_1$ is equal to the values of pA at $n=0.5$. The values of stability constants are listed in Table 1. The data show an increase in the value of $\log k_1$ with increase in temperature. The order of stability constant at 30 and 40° has been found to be Sm(III) > Nd(III) > Pr(III) > Ce(III) > La(III).

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Metal ions	$\log k_1$		$-\Delta G$ (k cal/mole)		ΔH (k cal/mole)	ΔG (Cal/mole/degree) 30°
	30°	40°	30°	40°		
La ³⁺	4.50	4.55	6.279	6.558	2.184	27.94
Ce ³⁺	4.55	4.59	6.349	6.616	1.747	23.42
Pr ³⁺	4.62	4.68	6.446	6.745	2.620	29.92
Nd ³⁺	4.70	4.78	6.558	6.890	3.493	33.16
Sm ³⁺	4.85	4.90	6.767	7.063	2.184	29.54

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been determined by using the temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation⁶. The values of these thermodynamic functions are summarised in Table 1. A perusal of the results shows that the value of free energies of formation becomes more negative with increase in temperature. It indicates that the complex formation process is spontaneous and the spontaneity increases with increase in temperature. It has also been noted that the value of stability constant increased with a rise in temperature. This indicates that the formation of all the complexes is an endothermic process. The complex formation is further favoured by the increase in the entropy of the system. It is indicated by the positive values of ΔS in all the cases.

The analysis of the results presented in Table 1 shows the low values of formation constants, free energy of formation and enthalpy changes for the systems under study. These values show that these metals have less tendency to form complexes with 2-furylglyoxal-2'-sulphonato anil.

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Kinetics of Ru(III) Catalysed Oxidation of Lactic Acid and Acrylic Acid by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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DESPITE much work on the oxidative capacity of alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) involving Os(VIII) as catalyst, little work has been done on the mechanism and path ways^{1,2} involved in Ru(III) catalysed oxidation of substrates by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III). Oxidation of lactic acid (LA) and acrylic acid (AA) by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) was found to proceed only in the presence of catalyst Ru(III). In the present communication, we report the kinetics and mechanism of Ru(III) catalysed oxidation of LA and AA by alkaline solution of hexacyanoferrate(III).

Experimental

Materials and method: Stock solutions of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) and sodium hydroxide were prepared from B.D.H., AnalaR reagents. The solution of ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Mathey) was prepared by dissolving the salt in hydrochloric acid of known strength. Lactic acid was Adamson (U.S.A.) and acrylic acid was E. Merck products. All other reagents were of A. R. grade except ferroin indicator (E. Merck).

The reaction was initiated by transferring the requisite quantity of substrate to the rest of the reaction mixture maintained at constant temperature. The kinetics were followed titrimetrically³ by examining aliquot portions of the reaction mixture for the consumed hexacyanoferrate(III).

Stoichiometry: The reaction mixture containing a known excess of hexacyanoferrate(III) over substrate was kept at 40° in presence $0.8 \times 10^{-1} M$ alkali and $3.52 \times 10^{-6} M$ Ru(III) in LA, and $5.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ alkali and $8.8 \times 10^{-6} M$ Ru(III) in AA oxidations. The amount of hexacyanoferrate(III) left revealed 1 : 2 stoichiometry between LA and hexacyanoferrate(III) and 1 : 8 stoichiometry between AA and hexacyanoferrate(III) as shown by eqns (1) and (2), respectively.

Presence of keto acid was detected by spot test⁴ as an end product in oxidation of LA while formic acid was identified by chromatography in oxidation of AA.

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TABLE 1

Lactic acid (LA) oxidation

$[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	1.25	1.44	1.67	2.00	2.50	3.32	5.00	6.60
$(-dc/dt)^a \times 10^5 \text{ mole lit}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.56	1.66	1.56	1.52	1.66	1.66	1.70	1.66
a $[\text{Ru}(\text{III})] = 3.52 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 10.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{LA}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, Temp. 30° .								
$[\text{LA}] \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	0.66	0.83	1.00	1.25	1.66	2.00	2.50	—
$(-dc/dt)^b \times 10^5 \text{ mole lit}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.16	1.62	2.09	2.34	3.09	3.85	5.10	—
$(-dc/dt) \times 10^5 / [\text{LA}] \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.78	1.95	2.09	1.87	1.86	1.92	2.04	—
b $[\text{Ru}(\text{III})] = 3.52 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, Temp. 30° .								
$[\text{NaOH}] \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	6.60	8.00	10.00	13.00	20.00	22.20	—	—
$(-dc/dt)^c \times 10^5 \text{ mole lit}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	2.18	1.94	1.83	1.47	1.10	0.96	—	—
c $[\text{Ru}(\text{III})] = 3.52 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, $[\text{LA}] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, Temp. 30° .								
$[\text{Ru}(\text{III})] \times 10^6 \text{ M}$	0.88	1.76	2.64	4.40	5.28	6.15	7.91	8.79
$(-dc/dt)^d \times 10^5 \text{ mole lit}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.95	0.81	0.93	1.87	2.20	2.65	3.35	3.61
$(-dc/dt) / [\text{Ru}(\text{III})] \text{ min}^{-1}$	4.01	4.61	3.54	4.25	4.17	4.31	4.23	4.10
d $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 10.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{LA}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, Temp. 30° .								

Acrylic acid (AA) oxidation

$[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	1.00	1.33	1.66	2.00	2.50	3.33	4.00	—
$(-dc/dt)^e \times 10^5 \text{ mole lit}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	2.80	2.83	2.90	3.04	3.14	3.23	3.10	—
e $[\text{Ru}(\text{III})] = 8.80 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{AA}] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, Temp. 30° .								
$[\text{AA}] \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	0.80	1.00	1.25	1.66	2.00	2.50	3.30	5.00
$(-dc/dt)^f \times 10^5 \text{ mole lit}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.71	0.80	1.20	1.50	1.55	2.00	2.80	4.00
$(-dc/dt) \times 10^5 / [\text{AA}] \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.88	0.80	0.96	0.90	0.78	0.80	0.84	0.80
f $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 10.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ru}(\text{III})] = 8.80 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, Temp. 30° .								
$[\text{NaOH}] \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	0.93	0.40	0.50	0.66	0.80	1.00	—	—
$(-dc/dt)^g \times 10^5 \text{ mole lit}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	3.20	2.66	2.40	2.00	1.75	1.55	—	—
g $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{AA}] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ru}(\text{III})] = 8.80 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, Temp. 30° .								
$[\text{Ru}(\text{III})] \times 10^6 \text{ M}$	2.20	3.80	4.40	6.60	7.70	9.90	12.10	—
$(-dc/dt)^h \times 10^5 \text{ mole lit}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.88	1.33	1.75	2.66	3.00	4.00	5.00	—
$(-dc/dt) / [\text{Ru}(\text{III})] \text{ min}^{-1}$	4.00	4.03	3.98	4.04	3.89	4.04	4.13	—
h $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{AA}] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, Temp. 30° .								

Results and Discussion

LA-hexacyanoferrate(III) and AA-hexacyanoferrate(III) reactions were studied at several initial [reactants] (Table 1). In both the reactions, the concentration-time plots in hexacyanoferrate(III) were linear suggesting zero-order dependence of the reactions on [hexacyanoferrate(III)]. Pseudo-zero order rate constant $(-dc/dt)$ values in hexacyanoferrate(III) were nearly constant at all [hexacyanoferrate(III)]. This further established zero-order kinetics with respect to [hexacyanoferrate(III)]. Pseudo-zero order constant $(-dc/dt)$ in hexacyanoferrate(III) increased uniformly with increase in [substrate]. The reactions, therefore, have first order dependence on [substrate], and the average first-order rate constants $\{k_1 = (-dc/dt)/[\text{substrate}]\}$ have been calculated as 1.93 ± 0.08 and $0.84 \pm 0.05 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for the oxidation of LA and AA respectively under the conditions of Table 1. The results of the effect of variation of [alkali] and $[\text{Ru}(\text{III})]$ are recorded in Table 1. Pseudo-zero order rate constant $(-dc/dt)$ value decreases on increasing [alkali] in both the cases. The nearly constant values of $(-dc/dt)/[\text{Ru}(\text{III})]$ at different $[\text{Ru}(\text{III})]$ clearly indicate first-order kinetics in

$[\text{Ru}(\text{III})]$. Insignificant effect of change in ionic strength (effected by addition of KCl) and [hexacyanoferrate(II)] was observed. The effect of temperature was quite marked. The values of zero-order rate constants $(-dc/dt)$ at 25, 30, 35 and 40° are 1.04, 1.32, 1.62 and $2.15 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mole lit}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$, respectively at $3.52 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$ $\text{Ru}(\text{III})$ and 0.1 M NaOH in oxidation of $1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ lactic acid and 2.41, 3.04, 5.00 and $6.66 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mole lit}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$, respectively at $8.80 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$ $\text{Ru}(\text{III})$ and 0.05 M NaOH in oxidation of $2.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ acrylic acid. The values of energy of activation and entropy of activation are 9.21 k cal/mole and -27.40 e.u. , respectively for LA and 14.74 k cal/mole and -10.26 e.u. , respectively for AA oxidation.

Ruthenium(III) chloride exists as $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ in dilute hydrochloric acid⁵. Such type of aquo-complexes are also reported to exist in the form of $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ in equilibrium with aquo-form.

The dissociation (3) would be highly favoured in alkaline medium, suggesting that $\text{Ru}(\text{III})$ chloride might exist as $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{6-x}(\text{OH})_x]^{(3-x)+}$ in alkaline medium. Since our kinetic observations show first-order dependence in $\text{Ru}(\text{III})$ and substrate, their

interaction appears to constitute a primary rate determining step. The zero-order kinetics in hexacyanoferrate(III) clearly suggests its involvement in a fast step only. The reaction pathways are given below

where $\text{S} = \text{CH}_3\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{COO}^-$ or $\text{CH}_2 = \text{CHCOO}^-$

where $\text{S}^+ = \text{CH}_3\overset{\oplus}{\text{C}}(\text{OH})\text{COO}^-$ or $\text{CH}_2 = \overset{\oplus}{\text{C}}\text{COO}^-$

The proposed mechanism involves the formation of an intermediate species in step (I) between Ru(III) species and anion of the substrate with possible exchange of a hydroxide ion coordinated to the central metal ion. The species thus formed undergoes disproportionation yielding the carbonium radical via the hydride ion abstraction from the α -carbon atom of substrate ion by Ru(III) species. The metal hydride then undergoes rapid oxidation by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in the subsequent step yielding initial Ru(III) species. The carbonium radical thus produced in the system will react rapidly with the hydroxyl ion producing keto acid and formic acid in oxidation of lactic acid and acrylic acid, respectively.

Applying steady state treatment to the intermediate species $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{6-x}(\text{OH})_{x-1}\text{S}]^{(4-x)+}$ and making the reasonable assumption that $k_2 + k_{-1}[\text{OH}^-] \gg k_1[\text{S}]$, the following limiting rate law is obtained.

$$\frac{-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}}{dt} = \frac{nk_1k_2[\text{Ru(III)}][\text{substrate}]}{k_2 + k_{-1}[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \text{... (4)}$$

where n is the number of moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) consumed in oxidation of molar [substrate]. Eqn. (4) is in complete agreement with the experimental results and thus supports the mechanism.

The independent nature of reaction rate on the ionic strength of the medium and the values of energy and entropy of activation also conform to the rate controlling step (I). The retarding trend due to $[\text{OH}^-]$ is also obvious from the rate law (4).

The proposed mechanism involves hydride ion transfer from α -carbon atom of substrate to Ru(III) species resulting in the metal hydride. This has been confirmed by examining the oxidation of tertiary butanol for more than 10 hr. Tertiary butanol having no α -carbon atom was not oxidised. This clearly offers an evidence in favour of involvement of hydrogen atom attached to the α -carbon atom of both the substrates.

In the proposed mechanism, the rate controlling step (I) involves interaction between oppositely charged ions and thus should correspond to a negative primary salt effect. However, addition of salt will involve an increase in the concentration of substrate and consequently a positive secondary salt effect. If both primary and secondary salt effects are determined by charge alone, there should be no net salt effect⁶. The salt effect observed in our case is consistent with this interpretation.

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Studies on the Adsorption and Salt Tolerance of Rosin Sulpho Sodium Oleates at Liquid/Liquid Interface

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INTERFACIAL tension parameters are responsible for enhanced oil recovery by surfactant flooding. It has been established¹⁻³ that for successful enhanced oil recovery the interfacial tension should be of the order of 10^{-3} dynes/cm. In view of this, petroleum sulphonates⁴⁻⁸ and their formulations⁹ have been used to achieve ultra low interfacial tension and several patents¹⁰⁻¹⁴ exist for their use in oil recovery. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile